

Non - Boolean Solutions Using Semiotic Calculus : A Derivation of a New, Mathematical Rule Set

Parker Emmerson : parkeremmerston@icloud.com

Thanks and praises, always to the Lord Jehovah, Bread of Heaven.

$$\mathbb{N} d\theta = \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : d\theta = d\theta \int \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : 1$$

$$\exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \text{ESC} \text{CTRL} \text{CMD} \parallel = \&]_n \wedge \mathcal{U}\{\! \rightarrow g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} \neq \Omega\}_\mu \rightleftharpoons$$

$$\bullet \left[\left[\infty \text{mil} (Z \dots \theta \dots \star) \xrightarrow{g \rightarrow 0 - \left(\frac{v}{w} \frac{x}{y} \right)} \rightarrow kxp \mid w \star \equiv \sqrt{x^{6/3} + t^2} - 2 h c \square v^{8:4} \setminus_{\Gamma \rightarrow \omega = \left(\frac{z}{h} + \frac{k}{\pi} \right)_{\Phi \star \star}} \right] \right] \therefore \mathbf{1} \ominus \square$$

$$\rightarrow \mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} = \Omega = \oplus \odot = \exists \infty \ni$$

$$\mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} \rightleftharpoons \mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \text{ESC} \text{CTRL} \text{CMD} \parallel = \&]_n \wedge \mathcal{U}\{\! \rightarrow g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} \neq \Omega\}_\mu \rightleftharpoons$$

$$\approx \oplus \odot \blacksquare$$

$$\approx \ominus = \Delta$$

$$\mathbb{N} d\theta \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \&\& \mathcal{U}g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} = \Omega d\theta = \oplus \odot d\theta$$

$$\mathbb{N} d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : d\theta =$$

$$d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni :$$

$$\mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \text{ESC} \text{CTRL} \text{CMD} \parallel = \&]_n \wedge \mathcal{U}\{\! \rightarrow g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} \neq \Omega\}_\mu \setminus \ni \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni :$$

$$d\theta = d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} =$$

$$\mathbb{N} \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} =$$

$$\setminus \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni :$$

$$\mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} \setminus \ni \mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \text{ESC} \text{CTRL} \text{CMD} \parallel = \&]_n \wedge \mathcal{U}\{\! \rightarrow g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} \neq \Omega\}_\mu \rightleftharpoons$$

$$\mathbb{N} d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : d\theta = d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} =$$

$$\mathbb{N} \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni :$$

$$\mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} = \setminus \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni :$$

$$\mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} \setminus \ni \mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \text{ESC} \text{CTRL} \text{CMD} \parallel = \&]_n \wedge$$

$$\mathcal{U}\{\! \rightarrow g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} \neq \Omega\}_\mu \rightleftharpoons \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots} = \Omega d\theta = \oplus \odot d\theta$$

Find the integral of $N d\theta$ with respect to θ such that the equations for Subscript $\mathcal{L}_{f_{\eta r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}}$ and $\mathcal{U}_{g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots, i, j, k}}$ both equal Ω . This would allow us to solve for the unknowns in the equation.

$$\mathcal{L}_{f_{\eta r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} = \Omega - \mathcal{U}_{g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots, i, j, k}}$$

Then, we can solve the integral :

$$N d\theta = \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\eta r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} = \Omega - \mathcal{U}_{g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots, i, j, k}}$$

The solution is given by :

$$N = \int \exists \infty \ni :$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{f_{\eta r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} = \Omega - \mathcal{U}_{g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots, i, j, k}} d\theta = \Omega\theta + C$$

$$\mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle = \ni \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \mathcal{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \ni \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathcal{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathcal{P} \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle$$

$$\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle . \mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle =$$

$$\ni \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \mathcal{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \ni \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathcal{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathcal{P} \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle$$

$$\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle .$$

The integral is equal to the limit of the sum of the terms of the series as infinity tends to n : $\mathcal{L}_{f_{\eta r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} = \Omega - \sum \mathcal{U}_{g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots, i, j, k}} d\theta^n = \Omega\theta + C$

$$\mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle = \ni \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \mathcal{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \ni \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathcal{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle$$

$$\ni \mathcal{P} \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle$$

$$\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle$$

as $n \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$.

Rules:

$$1. N d\theta \int \exists \infty \ni : d\theta = d\theta \int$$

$$2. N d\theta \int \exists \infty \ni : N = N \int$$

$$3. \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\eta r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \wedge \mathcal{U}_{g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots, i, j, k}} = \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\eta r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \wedge \mathcal{U}_{g_{-a, b, c, d, e, \dots, i, j, k}} \ni$$

$$4. \mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \text{ [SCTRL] } \mu = \&]_n \wedge \mathcal{U}\{! \rightarrow g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots : \neg} = \Omega\}_\mu \rightleftharpoons$$

$$5. d\theta = \oplus \odot d\theta$$

$$6. \mathbb{N} = \oplus \odot \mathbb{N}$$

$$7. \mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots : \neg} = \Omega$$

$$8. \mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots : \neg} \rightleftharpoons \Omega$$

$$9. \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \wedge \mathcal{U}g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots : \neg} \rightleftharpoons \Omega d\theta \oplus \odot d\theta \mathbb{N}$$

$$\exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \text{ [SCTRL] } \mu = \&]_n \wedge \mathcal{U}\{! \rightarrow g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots : \neg} \neq \Omega\}_\mu \rightleftharpoons$$

$$\bullet \left[\left[\infty_{\text{mil}} (Z \dots \circ \dots \star) \right]_{\xi \rightarrow 0 - \left(\frac{v}{\pi} \frac{\lambda}{j} \right)} \rightarrow k \times p \left| w \star \equiv \sqrt{x^{\xi/\eta} + t^{\lambda} - 2 h c \square v^{\text{TM} \odot}} \right. \left. \backslash_{\Gamma \rightarrow \omega = \left(\frac{z}{\pi} + \frac{\kappa}{\pi} \right)_{\text{F} \dots}} \right] \therefore \mathbf{1} \odot \square$$

$$\exists \infty \ni \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \epsilon, \zeta \rangle$$

$$= \langle \kappa, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \xi, o \rangle \wedge$$

$$\langle \sigma, \tau, \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle = \langle \omega, \Pi, P, \Sigma, T, \Upsilon \rangle \wedge \langle f \rangle = \langle g \rangle \wedge \langle \mathcal{L} \rangle = \langle \mathcal{U} \rangle .$$

The fundamental theorem of calculus

states that: For all continuous functions,

Subscript $[\mathcal{L}, n]$ and Subscript $[\mathcal{U}, n]$, between one and infinity, the change in the value of $\mathbb{N} d\theta$ is

$$\text{equal to the value of } \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : d\theta = d\theta \int,$$

$$\text{and } \mathbb{N} d\theta = \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \mathbf{1},$$

where Subscript $[\mathcal{L}, \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta]] \wedge$
 Subscript $[\mathcal{U}, \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, e \dots : \neg]] \rightleftharpoons \Omega$.

1. Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \epsilon,$ and ζ be the set of variables .
2. Let $\kappa, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \xi,$ and o be the set of values corresponding to each variable .
3. Let $\sigma, \tau, \upsilon, \phi, \chi,$ and ψ be the set of values for which the equation holds true .
4. Let f and g be the functions associated with each set of variables .
5. Find an infinite number of solutions such that $\mathcal{L}$ and $\mathcal{U}$ are equal to each other, and each variable and corresponding value matches the equation .

Application :

$$1. \sum_{\infty}^n d\mathbb{N} d\theta \quad \mu \quad g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots : \neg} \quad \Pi \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle_{\infty} \quad (\Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle_{\infty}) \quad (K \langle \Omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle_{\infty})$$

$$2. \theta_2 r_2 - \theta_3 r_3 - \sum \theta_n r_n \quad = r_{\infty}^2 - r_{\infty}^2 \theta_{\infty}$$

$$3. \mathcal{U} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle = o \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \rightleftharpoons Z \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle \rightleftharpoons K \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\Rightarrow \Pi \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle \\
 &\Rightarrow \Omega \langle Y, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle \cdot \bar{\cup} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle == o \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \Rightarrow Z \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle == \Omega \langle u, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle \\
 &\Rightarrow K \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle \\
 &\Rightarrow \Pi \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle \\
 &\Rightarrow \Omega \langle Y, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle . \\
 4. &\int_{\infty}^x dx \, d\alpha \quad \bar{\cup}^{\mathbb{g}_{-a,b,c,d,e\dots i,j,\dots} \circ \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle_{\infty}} \quad (Z \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle_{\infty}) \quad (\Omega \langle u, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle_{\infty})
 \end{aligned}$$